

Impact of Diffraction on Terahertz Compressed Sensing Single-Pixel Imaging

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Abstract—Terahertz (THz) single-pixel imaging, through compressive sensing, enables sampling below Nyquist rates and bypasses the need for mechanical scanning and the limitation of availability of high-resolution cost-effective THz imaging array detectors off-the-shelf. This research investigates how diffraction phenomena affect THz single-pixel imaging and properties of sensing matrices, along with the sparse signal reconstruction process. We introduce a variety of strategies designed to mitigate the effects of diffraction, along with novel methods to counteract the disruptions caused by THz physics, thereby preserving the integrity of the original sensing matrix and improving signal recoverability. A comprehensive simulation study sheds light on the effects of diffraction on the sensing matrices and their impact on signal reconstruction. Our results highlight the importance of accurate diffraction minimization techniques and sophisticated modelling in enhancing THz imaging systems.

Index Terms—Terahertz imaging, single-pixel imaging, diffraction, sensing matrices, sparse signal reconstruction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terahertz (THz) imaging is a rapidly evolving technology [1], finding applications in diverse fields such as material characterization, security screening, and non-invasive imaging, among others [2]. However, persistent challenges stem from the scarcity of simple, cost-effective high-resolution array detectors. The high costs and complexities associated with fabricating THz array detectors [3], [4] capable of operating at room temperature hinders the practical implementation of THz imaging systems. Consequently, mechanical scanning with a limited number of detector elements is often employed, compromising the balance between resolution and scanning time [5].

A promising solution is found in THz single-pixel imaging, augmented by compressive sensing (CS), which enables high-resolution imaging without the need for large and expensive detector arrays [6], [7]. Recent advancements in CS algorithms and optically-controlled Spatial Light Modulation (SLM) have significantly improved the efficiency and image quality achievable with single-pixel setups, offering a viable alternative for applications requiring high-resolution THz imaging [8], [9].

CS allows sampling signals at rates lower than dictated by the Shannon-Nyquist theorem for sparse signals [10]. By exploiting sparsity, signals can be efficiently reconstructed from fewer measurements given a well-conditioned linear sampling operator [11]. Various sensing matrices respecting

Fig. 1: Transmission and reflection setups used to analyze the effect of diffraction in the sensing model.

the Restricted Isometric Property (RIP), such as Fourier [12], Bernoulli [13], Hadamard [14], Gaussian [15], and Low-Density Parity Check Code matrices [16], have been studied and proven to allow for low-rate sampling. However, in the THz spectral range, diffraction and other nonlinear effects can modify the properties of sensing matrices, affecting signal reconstruction quality and guarantee of signal recovery [17].

This paper investigates the impact of diffraction on THz single-pixel imaging by analyzing the modification of modulation patterns and its effects on signal recovery. We demonstrate how the relationship between the desired sensing matrices and the THz response is impacted by the design choices, and illustrate methods for reducing the divergence between the desired sensing matrices and realistic sensing matrix accounting for THz response’s properties. We conduct simulations considering variations in pixel dimensions and modulation depths to assess their impact on imaging quality and resolution. Our results emphasize the necessity of accurate diffraction modelling in THz imaging systems.

II. DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS IN SINGLE-PIXEL THZ IMAGING

To comprehensively explore the significance of diffraction analysis in single-pixel THz imaging, we employ a straightforward experimental setup illustrated in Fig. 1. The subfigures portray a single-pixel imaging setup leveraging spatial modulation with different combinations of mask positions and in transmission or reflection mode.

Consider the "before" scenario for both reflective and refractive setup, represented by upscript^(ref1), where \mathbf{E} symbolizes the THz incident electric field radiation on the mask, independent of the mask (\vec{m}_i) and scene (\vec{x}). Upon modulation, the radiation diffracts to the scene following a linear propagation model given by $D_{(m2s)}$, and subsequently, it is collected at the detector after $D_{(s2d)}$ which accounts for diffraction between the scene and the detector. This process is summarized for each measurement, y_i , for a scene $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_i^{(\text{ref1})} &= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(s2d)} (\vec{x} \odot (D_{(m2s)} (\vec{m}_i \odot \mathbf{E}))) \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(s2d)} \text{diag}(\vec{x}) \text{vec}(D_{(m2s)} (\vec{m}_i \odot \mathbf{E})) \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(s2d)} \text{diag}(D_{(m2s)} (\vec{m}_i \odot \mathbf{E})) \vec{x} \\
&= 1^T D_{(s2d)} \text{diag}(D_{(m2s)} \vec{m}_i^{(\text{THz})}) \vec{x} \\
&= \underline{a}_i^{(\text{ref1})} \vec{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where \vec{m}_i^{THz} represents the i^{th} THz modulation pattern implemented at the spatial light modulator.

Similarly, for the "after" setup, represented by upscript^(ref2), the scene is illuminated with THz radiation \mathbf{E} , then diffracts to the mask following $D_{(s2m)}$, is modulated with \vec{m}_i to be collected after diffraction $D_{(m2d)}$. Hence each signal acquisition can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_i^{(\text{ref2})} &= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(m2d)} (\vec{m}_i \odot (D_{(s2m)} (\mathbf{E} \odot \vec{x}))) \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(m2d)} \text{diag}(\vec{m}_i) D_{(s2m)} (\mathbf{E} \odot \vec{x}) \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^n D_{(m2d)} \text{diag}(\vec{m}_i) D_{(s2m)} \text{diag}(\mathbf{E}) \vec{x} \\
&= 1^T D_{(m2d)} \text{diag}(\vec{m}_i) D_{(s2m)} \text{diag}(\mathbf{E}) \vec{x} \\
&= \underline{a}_i^{(\text{ref2})} \vec{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

This analysis accurately accounts for the potential discrepancy between the characteristics of the intended sensing matrix $M = [\vec{m}_i^T]_{i=1}^m$ and the actual THz sensing matrix $A = [\underline{a}_i]_{i=1}^m$, a discrepancy that arises due to the alterations induced by THz physical phenomena on the imaging patterns. In the following analysis, we embark on a detailed examination aimed at reducing the disparity between the anticipated and observed modulation effects:

A. Uniformity in Source Beam Profile Illumination

Due to the source profile (for example, the Gaussian profile in our simulation) even after collimation, the incident amplitude of \mathbf{E} , may vary across the mask (or scene depending on the design). To counteract this, we need to design and position the lens properly (eg. positioning in the far field) to ensure

an approximately constant amplitude and phase across the beam, symbolized by $e_{ij} \approx \alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ for each $e_{ij} \in \mathbf{E}$, leading to a simplified expression for the measured signal:

$$\vec{y} \approx \alpha A^{(\text{I})} \vec{x}. \tag{3}$$

B. Uniformity in Pixel Detection

Aiming that the scene-to-detector (or mask-to-detector) propagation is thus approximately modelled by a global attenuation and phase shift, we assume a constant detection contribution $\beta_{ii} \approx \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ for each $\beta_{ii} \in D_{(s2d)}$ (or $D_{(m2d)}$), simplifying the signal equation to:

$$\vec{y} \approx \alpha \beta A^{(\text{I,II})} \vec{x}. \tag{4}$$

Several methods can be used to achieve this, such as minimizing the distance from the collecting lens to the scene (or mask depending on the design), or by means of a collective lens in the far field.

C. Minimizing Diffraction Discrepancies

The constants α and β in (4) do not affect the properties of the sensing matrix, becoming just a rescaling factor, and hence do not limit the attainable image reconstruction quality.

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{a}_i^{(\text{I,II,ref1})} &= 1^T \text{diag}(D_{(m2s)} \vec{m}_i) \\
&= \overline{(D_{(m2s)} \vec{m}_i)^H}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{a}_i^{(\text{I,II,ref2})} &= \vec{m}_i^T \overline{(D_{(m2s)})^H} \\
&= 1^T \text{diag}(\vec{m}_i) D_{(s2m)} \\
&= \vec{m}_i^T \text{diag}(\vec{1}) D_{(s2m)} \\
&= \vec{m}_i^T D_{(s2m)}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Hence combining both design principles (II-A and II-B) simplifies the analysis of the deviation between M and A to the diffraction between the scene and the mask. Methods to minimize the diffraction between the scene and mask would help in minimizing the divergence of properties such as coherence, a method in CS to ensure the recoverability of the sparse signal.

Such methods include verifying that the pixel dimensions of the mask are sufficiently large compared to the propagating wavelength, minimizing the distance between the mask and the scene, or combining both. By optimizing such that diffraction $D_{(s2m)}$ or $D_{(m2s)}$ approaches a diagonal matrix, one can infer that $\vec{a}_i^{(\text{I,II,ref1/ref2})} \approx \vec{m}_i^{\text{opt}} = \vec{m}_i^{(\text{THz})}$.

D. SLM Pixel Detection Analysis

We can reformulate our question and consider each pixel point on the mask as a detecting element and rewrite the mask response in terms of detection response. The measurements $\vec{y} = [y_i]_i^n$ and $\underline{a}_i^{(\text{I,II,ref1})}$, $\underline{a}_i^{(\text{I,II,ref2})}$ can be expressed in the form $y_i = \vec{m}_i^T D \vec{x} = \vec{m}_i^T \vec{x}^{(\text{III})}$. The matrix D represents a diffraction matrix, particularly in physical optics with a specified sampling rate. The measurements \vec{y} can then be further expressed as:

$$\vec{y}^{(\text{I,II,III,ref1/ref2})} = \alpha \beta M D \vec{x} \tag{7}$$

Where $\vec{x}^{(\text{III})}$ is the diffracted representation of the image vector \vec{x} . Consequently, it can be equivalently expressed as:

$$\vec{y}^{(\text{I,II,III,ref1/ref2})} = \alpha\beta M\vec{x}^{(\text{III})}, \quad (8)$$

using $\vec{x}^{(\text{III})}$ as the desired reconstruction vector. When $\text{rank}(D) = n$, the image response can be obtained from the represented as $\vec{x} = D^{-1}\vec{x}^{(\text{III})}$.

E. Near Field and Diagonal Diffraction Matrix

In the near field and under minimal diffraction conditions, such as those described above, the diffraction matrix can be well-approximated as a diagonal matrix. Consequently, we have the following equalities and approximations:

$$\vec{y} = \alpha\beta MD\vec{x} \quad (9)$$

$$\approx \alpha\beta M(\gamma I)\vec{x} \quad (10)$$

$$\approx \alpha\beta\gamma M\vec{x} \quad (11)$$

These relations indicate that the measurements can be obtained as a projection through the measurement matrix of the scene response function \vec{x} , which corresponds to the actual commanded mask M . Thus, the properties of the measurement matrix coincide with those of the actual mask.

Hence, Equations (9), (10), and (11) describe a relationship in which the desired sensing matrix and the resulting sensing matrix share approximately the same properties, which arises in near field THz imaging and large pixel dimension THz imaging.

F. Optical Switch-Based SLM Dynamics

This section addresses the unique characteristics of optical switch-based SLMs, which utilize near-infrared (NIR) light for modulation. Unlike mechanical switches, optical switches introduce variability in the commanded mask's properties, necessitating a nuanced approach to achieve the desired modulation [18]. However, achieving unit modulation depth necessitates a high-power NIR source which may not be available in practice. The limited modulation depth affects the properties of the commanded mask.

For instance, conventionally, the Bernoulli sensing matrix is such that $m_{ij} \in M$, where $m_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ or $\{-1, 1\}$. When the optical switch-based SLM is employed, this transforms to $m_{ij}^{(\text{V})} \in \{m_1, m_2\}$, where $0 \leq m_1 < m_2 \leq 1$. Consequently, the modified matrix is denoted as $M^{(\text{V})} \in \{m_1, m_2\}^{m \times n}$. The properties of the original matrix M and the modified version $M^{(\text{V})}$ may diverge, potentially impacting the efficiency of the recovery process.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Experimental validation of the impact of pixel dimension

To evaluate the impact of diffraction on the modification of sensing matrices and recoverability of the signal, we conducted a GRASP [19]—a golden standard software for reflector antenna analysis—experimental simulations to

(a) Squares scene

(b) Siemens star scene

Fig. 2: Target scene used for signal reconstruction evaluation, squares for simplicity and Siemens star for complexity.

emulate the THz single-pixel imaging system in Fig. 1a. At a frequency of 750 GHz a gaussian beam was generated, with beam width of 1mm, with the distance between the mask and scene of 0.0512m and from the mask to the collecting lens being 0.1 m; 64×64 random Bernoulli masks were simulated with square pixel dimensions varying from 0.2 mm to 1.6 mm, approximately $\frac{1}{2}\lambda$ to 4λ . Several designs of sensing matrix for sparse image recovery were compared, namely

- **method A:** the usage of M like done in most related work, such as [8], [20],
- **method B:** M with post-processing with inverse Fourier transform ($\vec{x} = D^{-1}\vec{x}^{(\text{III})}$) as done in [21], [22],
- **method C:** consideration of $A^{\text{I,II}}$ such as in [23], [24] in the context of sparse phase retrieval, and
- **method D:** our reconstruction matrix, A , which accounts for both diffraction and THz source profile.

The sparse retrieval method employed is Order Recursive Matching Pursuit (ORMP) [25] to allow quality signal reconstruction despite high intercolumn coherence resulting from diffraction. We sample at $m = 1500$ for $n = 4096$. To further enhance image sparsity, the Daubechies wavelet transformation [26] is employed. The evaluation of image quality and reconstruction efficacy is evaluated from figures with reconstruction images of scenes provided in Fig. 2. In addition, quantitative metrics are utilized, including the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [27], Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) [28], Contrast-to-Noise Ratio (CNR) [29], and the IMage(normalized) Mean Squared Error (IMMSE) [30]. Particularly, the $\text{CNR} = \frac{\mu_{\text{scene}} - \mu_{\text{background}}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\text{scene}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{background}}^2}}$ metric is emphasized, given its relevance in the analysis of binary target scene images, where it effectively reflects the outcomes observable in the images (Note: μ_{scene} , $\mu_{\text{background}}$, σ_{scene} , and $\sigma_{\text{background}}$ denote the mean intensities and variances of the scene and background, respectively).

B. Experimental simulation of the impact of depth of spatial modulation

By defining the modulation depth as $\text{mod} = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{m_2}$, in this simulation, we demonstrated how the modulation depth impacts the signal reconstruction using random Bernoulli patterns. The measurements obtained were then used to reconstruct the target in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b using sparse retrieval methods for different values of the modulation depth.

Fig. 3: Correlation between the amplitude of the GRASP and linear model (M , $A^{(I,II)}$, and A) approximation averaged across different square pixel sizes.

Fig. 4: Reconstruction at pixel size of 2λ with method A, B, C, and D as defined in section III-A.

Fig. 5: Image reconstruction with method A as defined in III-A at different pixel size at $\frac{1}{2}\lambda$, λ , 2λ , 3λ , and 4λ .

Metric / Method	A	B	C	D
SSIM	0.6769	0.6743	0.6769	0.6769
PSNR	9.1954	9.1760	9.2282	9.2282
CNR	1.7549	2.5245	3.0760	3.0759
IMMSE	0.1204	0.1209	0.1195	0.1195

TABLE I: Comparison of reconstruction using method A, B, C, and D as defined in section III-A.

Metric / Pixel Size	$\lambda/2$	λ	2λ	3λ	4λ
SSIM	0.6446	0.6707	0.6779	0.6704	0.6658
PSNR	9.1060	9.1267	9.2455	9.4473	9.6389
CNR	0.5490	1.2627	2.2452	2.9265	2.9806
IMMSE	0.1229	0.1223	0.1190	0.1136	0.1088

TABLE II: Comparison of image quality metrics for different pixel sizes with method A as defined in III-A

Fig. 6: Image reconstructed with method A, M , at large pixel dimension, 2λ , with different modulation depths $\text{mod} = [0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1]$ without consideration of the modulation depth.

Fig. 7: Image reconstructed with method A, M , at large pixel dimension, 2λ , with different modulation depths $\text{mod} = [0.1, 0.2, \dots, 1]$ with consideration of modulation depth.

C. Results and Discussion

1) Introduction to Pixel Dimension and Diffraction:

As pixel dimensions increase, the discrepancy caused by diffraction between the scene and its reconstruction diminishes. This enhancement bolsters the congruence between the anticipated measurement outcomes and the actual measurement outcomes. Consider, for instance, the scene depicted in Fig 2; Fig. 3 illustrates the increase in correlation between the expected measurement of the commanded mask, denoted as $\vec{y}^{(\text{opt})} = M\vec{x}$, and the ground truth THz measurement obtained through GRASP simulation, expressed as $\vec{y}^{(\text{GRASP})} = \text{graspSimulator}(\vec{x})$, as a function of increasing pixel dimensions. Furthermore, this example underscores the significance of employing linear sensing matrices that approximate diffraction effects, specifically $\vec{y}^{(\text{THzwoE})} = A^{(I,II)}\vec{x}$ and $\vec{y}^{(\text{THzwe})} = A\vec{x}$, as they demonstrate high correlation.

2) **On Sparse Signal Reconstruction:** Across various reconstructions utilizing sensing matrices, reconstructions performed with larger pixel dimensions yield superior outcomes compared to those with smaller dimensions. The fidelity of sparse signal reconstruction exhibits improvement inversely with diffraction augmentation as shown in Fig. 5 and Table II. Notably, reconstructions that account for diffraction effects, using A and $A^{(I,II)}$, surpass those that do not as shown in the example in Fig. 4 and Table I. Thanks to the design proposed in I, both A and $A^{(I,II)}$ show similar reconstruction ability; otherwise, the consideration of the Gaussian profile is necessary for performance efficiency across all pixels independent of the positioning in relationship to the centre of THz beam propagation.

3) **Optical Switch-based SLM and Modulation Depth:** In scenarios involving optical switch-based SLMs, the achieved modulation depth may deviate from its anticipated level. Using scene in Fig. 2 and employing high pixel dimensions to mitigate diffraction, the correlation between the desired mask pattern's measurement, $\vec{y}^{(\text{opt})}$, and the diffracted measurement, $\vec{y}^{(\text{THzwe})}$, show slight modification with modulation depth.

However, images reconstructed from measurements acquired without consideration of the modulation depths demonstrate superior quality to those from lower depths as shown in Fig. 6. Furthermore, the consideration of depth modulation in the reconstruction matrix yields better accuracy, as shown by comparing the results of Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. It is crucial, therefore, not to overlook modulation depth in design analyses. It should be noted that opting for high pixel dimensions and modulation depths influences both the size of the SLM and the required excitation power, given that the modulation depth is dependent on the power per unit area, which in turn affects the excitation area.

IV. CONCLUSION

The performance of sparse signal reconstruction in THz single-pixel cameras is significantly influenced by diffraction and modulation depth, which degrade the projected patterns and, consequently, the properties of the sensing matrix. We propose and demonstrate methods aimed at minimizing these alterations, preserving the original features of the sensing matrix as much as possible. Despite the tendency in existing research to overlook or only partially account for the effect of physical factors such as diffraction, the shape of the source profile, and modulation depth, our findings reveal their profound impact on the accuracy of sparse reconstructions.

By integrating essential elements into our sensing matrix model, we have attained greater accuracy in signal reconstruction than methods lacking them. This progress highlights the crucial role of thorough modelling in the THz imaging process, stressing the significance of a profound grasp and incorporation of such phenomena. Furthermore, mitigating the impacts of the latter, achieved through enlarging the mask pixel size in our study, leads to improved signal reconstruction. This underscores the critical importance of designing an appropriate hardware setup.

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